
Impact of Mass Failure in Measurement Courses on Quantity Surveying Students

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Abstract Since education is a complex process based on mutual interaction of many factors, examination failure is known to be based on different versatile reasons. This study examined the impact of mass failure in measurement courses on quantity surveying students. This study collected data through the use of structured questionnaire that were administered to staff and students in the department of quantity surveying in institutions offering quantity surveying as a course of study in Ondo state, Nigeria. Eighty-one (81) questionnaires were administered and sixty-eight (68) were retrieved. The data retrieved were analyzed using descriptive statistics, mean score response analysis, frequency and percentages. The study concluded that the impact of mass failure in measurement courses on quantity surveying students includes finishing with low grade, dropping out of school and unsuccessful academic life. In order to improve grades, reduce dropout rates, and foster successful academic outcomes, it is recommended to implement comprehensive academic support programs that address the specific challenges faced by students in measurement courses, these programs should include providing tutoring services, implementing early intervention strategies, and promoting effective study habits.

Keywords examination failure, impact of failure, mass failure, measurement courses, quantity surveying students

1. Introduction

Any educational establishment's success is heavily influenced by students' academic performance. Further developing understudies' instructive execution has been a serious worry to every nonpartisan inside the schooling area; this includes parents, teachers, students, faculty management, and government at every level. The sole justification behind descending pattern inside the instructive execution of researchers anyway conjointly because of their thinking to take understudies' instructive exhibition to future level.

Measurement courses are essential for aspiring professionals in the field of quantity surveying to acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. However, mass failure in these courses can have a significant impact on their academic progress and future careers. The purpose of this article is to examine the effects of widespread failure in measurement courses on students studying quantity surveying and to offer solutions. According to Igberadja (2016), educational performance is used in the classroom to assess students' success in learning certificate content through ongoing testing and assessment. Instructive execution is chosen with a money order and assessment scores or stamps relegated by the subject teachers. Educational performance is selected by check and examination scores or marks assigned by the courses lecturers (Adediwura and Tayo, 2007).

2. Literature review

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Karel and Woods (2008), demonstrates that vocational education is frequently regarded as a second chance in the majority of high school educational systems in western nations. Dropout, a negative learning attitude, low grades, and a lack of confidence undermine the educational system's goal of providing equal opportunities for all students (Beblavy, Thum, and Veselkova, 2011), which causes significant issues for individuals, the educational system, the community, and society as a whole. Inadequate instructional materials, equipment, and facilities, a lack of qualified lecturers, and difficulties interpreting questions and structuring the curriculum are all contributing factors to low performance in measurement courses in Nigerian institutions (Hauser, Warren, Huang, and Carter, 2000). In spite of the fact that the provision of resources has been associated with improved academic performance (Siddhu, 2011), it is essential to ensure that these resources are utilized appropriately (Engin-Demir, 2009). The absence of inspiration among graduate understudies, affected by both family support and the relationship with teachers, adds to unfortunate scholastic execution (Huitt, 2005). Mass failure in measurement courses can lead to academic failure, a lack of enthusiasm for learning, low motivation, increased stress, loss of control, and a lack of confidence (Christle, Jolivet, and Nelson, 2007). It can also lead to a lack of relevant curriculum structure and language.

Low grade: Mass disappointment in estimation courses frequently brings about low grades for understudies. Students' self-esteem, motivation, and academic standing can be negatively impacted by poor academic performance. A study by Chintapatla and Ramesh (2018) found that students who receive low grades have lower self-esteem and a sense of failure, which has a negative impact on their academic progress.

Leaving School Early: Some quantitative surveying students may consider dropping out of school if they consistently fail measurement courses. They may lose interest in pursuing their chosen career path as a result of their frustration and perceived academic failure. Di Pietro's (2020) research demonstrates that academic dissatisfaction and failure are significant predictors of student dropout rates.

Unsatisfactory Academic Life: Quantity surveying students' academic trajectory can be affected in the long run by widespread failure in measurement courses. It might make it harder for them to meet the requirements for graduation, which would make them stay in school longer and make it harder for them to get a job. Such postponements can thwart vocation movement and breaking point proficient open doors. A concentrate by Slemp, Chin, Kern, Siokou, Loton, and Oades (2019) observed that scholarly disappointment is related with expanded feelings of anxiety and decreased profession possibilities.

3. Research methodology

Data analysis, following the framework outlined by Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), involved organizing and deriving meaning from a substantial amount of information. While a quantitative research method was the preferred approach employed for analytical purposes. This study collected data through the use of structured questionnaire that were administered to staff and students in the department of quantity surveying in institutions offering quantity surveying as a course of study in Ondo state, Nigeria. Eighty-one (81) questionnaires were administered and sixty-eight (68) were retrieved. The data retrieved were analyzed using descriptive statistics, mean score response analysis, frequency and percentages.

4. Findings and discussion

Table 1 shows the number of questionnaire distributed is eighty-one (81) in numbers with 100%. The number of questionnaire completed and returned is sixty-three (63) which will be used for the analysis and computation of the data.

Table 1: Distribution of questionnaires

Type of response	Frequency	Percentage
Number distributed	81	100
Completed and returned	68	81.93
Number not returned	13	18.07

Source: Author (2023)

Table 2 shows that out of Sixty-eight (68) respondents, thirteen (13) of respondents are ND holders representing 20.00%, Twenty-two (22) of respondents are HND representing 33.8%, Seventeen (17) of respondents are BSc representing 26.2%, Six (6) of respondents are PGD representing 9.2%, Five (5) of respondents are MSC representing 7.7% and Five (5) respondents are PhD representing 7.5%. The highest majority is the HND holders followed by the BSc. holders.

Table 2: Academic qualification of respondents

Education background	Frequency	Percentage
ND	13	16
HND	22	33
BSc.	17	26
PGD	6	9
MSc.	5	8
PhD	5	8
Total	68	100

Source: Author (2023)

Table 3 shows the status involved in by the respondents. Lecturer represents 16.18% and student represents 83.82%. the highest percentage is the student.

Table 3: Status in the department

Status in the department	Frequency	Percentage
Lecturer	11	16
Student	57	84
Total	68	100

Source: Author (2023)

Table 4 shows the level of students in the department level 200 represent 15%, 300 represent 19%, 400 represent 44% and 500 represent 22%. The highest level of student is 400 level with 44% followed by 500 level with 22%.

Table 4: Level of students

Level of students	Frequency	Percentage
200	10	15
300	12	19
400	30	44
500	15	22
Total	68	100

Source: Author (2023)

Table 5 shows the response of the respondents on the impact of mass failure in measurement courses on quantity surveying students which is indicated below with different mean score and ranking which is as follows finishing with low grade with a mean score 3.86 which falls into 1st position, dropping out from school with a mean score (3.78) which falls into 2nd position, unsuccessful academic life with a mean score (3.75) which falls into 3rd position, low enthusiasm for learning (3.75) which falls into 3th position, lack of motivation for learning (3.75) which falls into 3th position, lack of interest in learning with a mean score (3.68) which falls into 6th position, weak willingness to learn with a mean score which falls into 7th position, poor learning mentality with a mean score (3.66) which falls into 8th position, inability to interpret questions with a mean score (3.64) which falls into 20th position, structuring of the curriculum with a mean score (3.62) which falls into 10th position, attitudes toward school with a mean score (3.60) which falls into 11th position, self-competence with a mean score (3.59) which falls into 12th position, behavior with a mean score (3.58) which falls into 13th position, loss of confidence with a mean score (3.58) which falls into 13th position, loss of control with mean score (3.56) which falls into 15th position, loss of confidence with a mean score (3.53) which falls into 16th position, lack of language structure with a mean score (3.41) which falls into 17th position, lack of relevant curriculum with a mean score (3.31) which falls into 18th position, low self-esteem with a mean score (3.15) which falls into 19th and low thinking ability with a mean score (3.14) which falls into 20th position.

Table 5: Impact of Mass Failure in Measurement Courses on Quantity Surveying Students

Options	Mean score	Rank
Finishing with low grade	3.86	1 st
Dropping out of school	3.78	2 nd
Unsuccessful academic life	3.75	3 rd
Low enthusiasm for learning	3.75	3 rd
Lack of motivation for learning	3.75	3 rd
Lack of interest in learning	3.68	6 th
Weak willingness to learn	3.67	7 th
Poor learning mentality	3.66	8 th
Inability to interpret questions	3.64	9 th
Structuring of the curriculum	3.62	10 th
Attitudes toward school	3.60	11 th
Self-competence	3.59	12 th
Behavior	3.58	13 th
Increased stress levels	3.58	13 th
Loss of control	3.56	15 th
Loss of confidence	3.53	16 th
Lack of language in structure	3.41	17 th
Lack of relevant curriculum	3.31	18 th
Low self-esteem	3.15	19 th
Low thinking ability	3.14	20 th

Source: Author (2023)

5. Conclusion

The study concluded that the impact of mass failure in measurement courses on quantity surveying students includes finishing with low grade, dropping out of school and unsuccessful academic life.

6. Recommendation

In order to improve grades, reduce dropout rates, and foster successful academic outcomes, it is recommended to implement comprehensive academic support programs that address the specific challenges faced by students in measurement courses, these programs should include providing tutoring services, implementing early intervention strategies, and promoting effective study habits.

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